

Exploring a Critical Methodological Gap in Measuring of Field-Differences in Survey Research: Insights into Scientific Data Sharing and Beyond

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Abstract: This study explores a critical methodological gap in accurately measuring differences across scientific fields within survey research. It focuses on analyzing field-differences in scientific data sharing practices. By examining existing methodologies, the study aims to shed light on the limitations of current field-comparative survey research and inspire the development of more robust methodologies. The study conducts a literature review of the state of the art of field-comparative survey designs by systematically analyzing survey studies on data sharing and the instruments used. Preliminary findings underscore a common reliance on formal discipline classifications to delineate variations in data sharing practices among fields, while also highlighting a dearth of studies explaining these differences. This indicates a need for more nuanced methodological approaches in survey literature considering epistemic properties that underpin knowledge production within specific fields.

1. Introduction

Thinking about dynamics between concepts of openness and closedness in science one of the most prominent topics is the development of the open data movement. The debate over whether to share or withhold research data is a crucial issue that holds significant relevance for the Science, Technology, and Innovation community, capturing its attention and raising important questions.

Previous research has illuminated various facets of this discourse. Scholars have explored moral, legal, and regulatory frameworks surrounding data sharing, delving into the ethical considerations, legal obligations, and policy implications that shape data sharing practices (e.g., Kitchin, 2014; Maxson Jones et al., 2018; Mirowski, 2018). Additionally, attention has been directed towards the intricate technological infrastructure challenges inherent in facilitating data sharing, including issues related to data interoperability, standardization, and accessibility (e.g., Borgman, 2017). Furthermore, researchers have investigated the diverse drivers for data sharing among scientists (e.g., Fecher et al., 2015; Haeussler et al., 2014). Motivations may range from the desire to advance scientific knowledge and foster collaboration to the recognition of professional incentives and mandates from funding agencies. However, despite these efforts, gaps persist in our comprehension of how these dimensions intertwine and impact data sharing practices across different scientific fields (Leonelli, 2022).

Considering the complicated dynamics of data sharing in science and the interplay between openness and closedness, an extensive understanding of this phenomenon necessitates a systematic approach. The study focuses on survey research and explores the methodological challenges in accurately capturing field-specific variations. Through an examination of research literature and survey instruments, the study aims to illuminate the methodological landscape of field-comparative survey research. Taking stock of insights gained so far through field comparative survey research on data sharing, it advocates for a broader consideration of underlying factors to explain field differences in scientific data sharing practices.

2. Research problem

To provide a clearer distinction within the complex phenomenon of scientific data sharing I divide these dimensions into three primary levels.

- Macro: These are external factors explicitly defined from outside of research process, such as political restrictions or mandates from funding organizations regarding data sharing practices.

- Meso: At this intermediary level, factors are shaped by the unique characteristics of the research process, which are typical for specific research fields. Examples include the routine utilization of gene banks in biotechnology research or the incorporation of official regulatory data in macroeconomic studies.

- Micro: In situations where there are no strict regulations or specific characteristics inherent in the research process, individuals make decisions about whether to share their data. These decisions can be influenced by potential benefits from sharing or constraints such as time and other individual resources required for the sharing process.

Data sharing practices often result from an interplay of factors across all three levels (e.g., Haas & Park, 2010), and it is beneficial to look at the phenomenon of data sharing from different perspectives. These may include gaining insights into the potential institutional barriers and incentives behind open science practices such as data sharing (e.g., Łobodzińska & Frankowska, 2023) and individual attitudes toward data reuse and sharing (e.g., Gregory et al., 2023). It is essential to recognize that the barriers and incentives influencing data sharing practices are not universally applicable to all researchers across diverse research communities. When investigating open data practices such as public data sharing, it is valuable to take into account field-specific differences in research practices (Velden & Tcypina, 2023).

Survey methodology allows for the collection of data across various levels, encompassing individual attitudes, experiences with field-specific research processes, and perceptions of regulations. Through carefully designed survey questions, researchers can gather insights into participants' beliefs, behaviors, and experiences related to data sharing practices. For example, survey questions can explore individuals' willingness to share their research data, their past experiences with data sharing, and the factors influencing their decisions. Additionally, researchers can inquire about participants' awareness of regulations and policies governing data sharing, as well as their attitudes towards these regulations. Thus, by employing surveys, researchers can gather rich and diverse data that span the macro, meso, and micro levels of data sharing dimensions. However, the standardized nature of survey methodology poses specific challenges when attempting to capture data sharing dimensions at the meso-level, where field-specific differences play a crucial role.

This challenge is not unique to research on data sharing. For survey research in science studies more generally there exists a critical methodological gap in accurately measuring differences across scientific fields. The formal discipline classifications only partially explain the field-differences because this approach implicates differences in types of research but does not delve into and identify the specific properties of research that relate to observed field differences. Moreover, relying solely on formal discipline classifications can distort results due to their limitations in capturing the variations within scientific fields. This approach may overlook the unique characteristics and contextual factors that contribute to differences in research practices and outcomes across disciplines. Specifically, it can lead to discrepancies between the population divided by disciplines and the division based on factors related to data sharing behaviors, highlighting the need for a more refined approach to field differentiation.

Therefore, in field-comparative survey studies, it would be beneficial to move beyond discipline classifications and stay closer to research practices by capturing epistemic properties of knowledge production to examine their relationship to the observed variation in the phenomenon of interest (Gläser, 2018). Epistemic properties encompass the fundamental

characteristics of how knowledge is produced and understood within specific fields of study. While the theoretical foundations for a broad application of the concept are being established, several studies employ epistemic properties, such as resource intensity or genericity of methods, as explanatory factors for various social processes. An illustrative instance is the qualitative exploratory study that examines the connections between epistemic properties and institutional conditions for research (Laudel & Gläser, 2014). Another example involves a study that explores how the development of individual research plans is shaped by the epistemic properties within scientific fields (Bielick & Laudel, 2018). Especially relevant for the research of the study is the research that delves into epistemic conditions and the causal mechanisms of scientific sharing across fields (Velden, 2013). It underscores the necessity of considering field-specific sources that contribute to variations in openness and sharing behaviors.

3. Aim of the study

The aim of this study is to explore and illuminate the dimensions of this methodological gap in accurately measuring differences across scientific fields within survey research. To exemplify the issues, the study examines the limitations and challenges that hinder the understanding of field-specific variations in data sharing practices as a phenomenon of interest. Through an examination of existing methodologies, the study aims to provide insights into the complexities of scientific data sharing and to inspire future survey research to develop more robust and accurate methodologies for assessing field-specific variations in data sharing practices and beyond. It is important to note that while some preliminary insights and findings are presented, this research is ongoing, and further analysis is underway.

The contribution reviews the state of the art in field-comparative survey research on data sharing, with regard to three central aspects:

- 1) The scientific field grouping schemes applied.
- 2) The epistemic properties that have been measured in order to explain variation in the phenomenon of interest.
- 3) The methodological approaches have been used to analyze the data regarding field differences in the phenomenon of interest.

The third aspect concerns two issues: the analysis of differences at the meso-level, and the investigation of relationships between grouping and data sharing dimensions. On the one hand the selected methods must have the capability to analyze differences between various groups within the surveyed population. These groups may be defined by scientific disciplines, institutional affiliations, demographic characteristics, or other relevant factors. Of particular interest to this study are groupings by research fields. By examining group differences, researchers can gain insights into how different segments of the population perceive and engage with scientific practices of data sharing. On the other hand, the chosen methods should be suitable for investigating relationships between different dimensions or variables within the surveyed data. This includes exploring correlations, associations, and causal pathways between field belonging and data sharing indicators. By examining these relationships, researchers can uncover underlying patterns and dynamics that contribute to understanding of scientific data sharing phenomena.

The aim of reviewing the literature with regard to the third aspect is to identify and evaluate methodological approaches that not only enable the analysis of group differences but also facilitate the exploration of complex relationships within survey data. By fulfilling these dual requirements, these methods contribute to advancing our understanding of scientific practices, behaviors, and dynamics within the context of scientific data sharing and beyond.

In summary, this research aims to contribute to the advancement of field-comparative survey research by focusing on three key methodological aspects. Through examination of these

characteristics, the study seeks to highlight the crucial limitations in current survey research regarding the analysis of field differences and to provide valuable insights that can inform future studies and contribute to the ongoing development of methodology in this area.

4. Methods and preliminary results

The approach is a literature review based on a state-of-the-art methodology, which consists of two distinct phases. The initial phase focuses on survey literature related to data sharing. The additional phase is motivated by the methodological limitations identified in the literature during the first phase. It aims to provide a more in-depth understanding of survey methodologies and epistemic considerations through a broader examination of field classifications within survey research. In the second phase, it was not feasible to assess all potential surveys; therefore, the decision was made to focus on core journals within Science and Technology Studies from the past eight years. While this approach may have excluded relevant contributions from non-core journals, it was necessary to ensure a systematic and manageable scope of analysis within the available resources.

4.1 Review of Survey-Literature on Data Sharing

The initial phase involves systematically analyzing research literature and survey instruments related to scientific data sharing over the past years using Google Scholar's search function. The search terms include combinations such as "open science data sharing survey," "open science data sharing," and "academic data sharing," or at least one of the words "survey," "data," or "sharing," for the years since 2016. Additionally, reference lists of identified publications were checked for relevant surveys.

The goal is to identify as many survey-based studies on scientific data sharing as possible by applying various combinations of keywords and publication years. Google scholar, and reference lists of items found through google scholar, were used to access to a broader range of sources, including articles, theses, books, and conference proceedings, which may not be indexed in traditional literature databases. This ensures that the research captures a comprehensive view of the survey-based literature on data sharing.

The literature review covered materials published from 2012 to 2023 and resulted in the identification of 81 survey-based contributions. Most of these are research articles, but also some reports were found. Systematically examining the literature allows for the identification of studies that satisfy the key selection criteria:

- the inclusion of field as a dimension in the survey,
- the consideration of field differences within the survey,
- the incorporation of epistemic properties within the survey,
- and the application of survey data analysis approaches to investigate the association between research field affiliation and the measurement of a phenomenon of interest.

Of the 81 publications identified, fourteen studies focused on a single field of researchers, while 67 examined at least two research fields, classifying them as field-comparative studies. The review highlighted a strong reliance on formal definitions of research fields, typically based on discipline assignment or institutional affiliation. Noteworthy examples among single-field studies include those that define a specific group as the producer of a particular data type, such as clinical trial researchers (Rathi, 2012; Tan et al., 2021) or qualitative social scientists (Jeng & He, 2022). Additionally, some studies combine data type with formal disciplinary distinctions, enhancing the sample's relevance for data-sharing investigations. Examples include Enke et al. (2012) on biodiversity data and Mozersky et al. (2021) on qualitative researchers.

I've categorized the approaches used in various studies on data sharing into four distinct types (Figure 1). More than one-third of the studies (32) rely solely on descriptive statistics, with sample sizes ranging from 100 to 3,000 respondents. The first type is descriptive associative,

where studies provide classical reports that describe data-sharing practices without exploring underlying reasons. The second type is descriptive causal, in which researchers directly ask participants about their reasons for sharing or not sharing data, offering a basic understanding of their motivations. Forty-nine studies employ advanced statistical techniques beyond basic descriptive methods. The third category, advanced associative, includes studies that use advanced statistical methods to explore associations between factors without establishing causality. The last category, advanced causal, includes analytical techniques like structural equation modeling to examine the reasons for data sharing or withholding and to identify causal relationships.

I've identified three author groups that use causal data analysis to explore factors in data sharing:

- 1) Stieglitz et al. (2020) focused on micro-level factors and did not address meso- or macro-levels.
- 2) Kim et al. (e.g., Kim & Burns 2016) examined factors at both individual and institutional levels.
- 3) Syahri et al. (2021) used a model similar to Kim et al.

For both Kim and Syahri, it remains unclear whether they distinguish between meso- and macro-levels, and if epistemic properties are included in their institutional effects.

<i>Category</i>	<i>descriptive</i>	<i>advanced statistical methods</i>
<i>non-causal</i>	Classical descriptive statistics in the form of reports	Association between Data Sharing and other parameters - Regression Modeling, ANOVA, Chi Squared test.
<i>causal</i>	Direct questioning about the possible reasons and obstacles to data sharing	Explorative or or theory-based hypothesis testing - Structural Modeling (SEM, PLS, LCA)

Figure 1: Data analysis approaches

Overall, the analysis of the selected literature underscores a diverse range of survey-based contributions, spanning from field-specific investigations to comparative analyses across multiple fields, applying advanced statistical techniques for data analysis. However, examples of studies that contribute to understanding the underlying factors governing field differences in data sharing are rare. Given the importance of data sharing in research, this observation may indicate a potential gap in field-comparative survey literature. At the same time, it is evident that data sharing was not the primary focus of all surveys considering field differences. Therefore, to gain a better understanding of how research fields are recorded in survey research, it would be beneficial to compare this finding with trends observed in the broader pool of survey literature.

4.2 Review of Survey-Literature in Core Journals

The subsequent step expands the initially selected topic of data sharing to include a general review of field-comparative survey research, while limiting the review to publications in ten core journals that focus on scientific content related to Science and Technology Studies. The

research covers the past eight years to provide a systematic overview of recent literature while ensuring that the analysis remains current and relevant.

The resulting corpus of literature includes 273 research articles based on the analysis of survey data (Table 1). The initial rough review of the studies enables the distinction between surveys that consider fields, indicating that the category of field was utilized in some form within the study. Some of these studies utilize fields for sample selection, with the analysis focusing on one specific field. Others, particularly relevant for this research, are field-comparative studies, where fields are applied for analysis across field categories. The highest number of survey-based studies were identified in the journals "Research Policy" (86), "Science and Public Policy" (63), and "Research Evaluation" (43), with almost an equal number of field-comparative studies across these three journals. In the "Journal of Informetrics" and the "Journal of Scientometric Research" were considered 5 survey-based articles in total, just one from them was labeled as field-comparative. The Journal "Social Studies of Science" was included in the initial examination, but no relevant surveys were found.

Table 1. Number of survey-studies by journals.

Journal	Number of survey-studies		
	total (considering fields)	single field	field-comparative
Quantitative Science Studies	9 (6)	1	5
Journal of Informetrics	2 (2)	1	1
Journal of Scientometric Research	3 (0)	0	0
Scientometrics	34 (29)	14	15
Science and Public Policy	63 (44)	17	27
Research Evaluation	43 (30)	3	27
Research Policy	86 (33)	7	26
Minerva	16 (13)	4	9
Science, Technology, & Human Values	17 (9)	2	7
Total	273 (166)	49	117

More than half of the considered survey studies utilize research field as a dimension but most of them rely on formal discipline classification to define research fields. Different to the prevalent trend in the collected survey literature on data sharing, a considerable portion of studies employ analytical tools beyond descriptive statistics. These are advanced statistical techniques, such as structural equation modeling (e.g., Gu et al. 2017), and various clustering approaches, including k-means (e.g., de Frutos-Belizón et al., 2023) or Ward's method (e.g., Aerni et al., 2015). Assessing the suitability of these approaches for capturing epistemic properties requires further in-depth analysis of the collected literature.

The preliminary analysis of the literature collected in phases 1 and 2 of this research has shown that relying on formal discipline classifications without considering epistemic properties presents a substantial methodological limitation, potentially overlooking valuable insights into field-specific nuances. Additionally, the prevalent use of descriptive approaches over statistical analysis to examine variations in data sharing practices suggests a missed opportunity for uncovering deeper insights into the driving factors behind these differences.

Following these preliminary findings, the next steps involve conducting an analysis of the studies found in both phases of the literature search with the focus on the data analysis approaches used in survey studies, including the statistical techniques and clustering

approaches applied to investigate field differences in data sharing behaviors and other phenomena of interest.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research examines the methodological landscape of field-comparative survey research with a particular focus on understanding field differences in scientific data sharing. Through the initial analysis of existing survey-literature, several key insights have emerged. While there has been progress in understanding of data sharing practices within the scientific community, this study illuminates critical gaps in current survey methodologies. Emphasizing the imperative to transcend formal discipline classifications and delve into the nuanced epistemic properties that shape field-specific variations, a call is made for a more refined approach to field differentiation. Additionally, the preliminary findings underscore the limitations of current survey approaches, including the scarcity of field-comparative studies and over-reliance on purely descriptive analyses. A reassessment of survey methodologies is reasonable to better meet the current research needs and objectives. By addressing these identified methodological gaps, researchers are better positioned to capture the intricacies of scientific data sharing practices across diverse fields.

Open science practices

This study is currently a work in progress. Upon completion, the final literature analysis results will be made openly available, emphasizing transparency and enabling further exploration by the scientific community. This commitment ensures that methodologies and findings are accessible for scrutiny, fostering a culture of transparency and collaboration in scientific research.

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Competing interests

No competing interests.

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